

SPECIFIC CHARACTERISTICS OF MEDICAL TERMS: BASED ON THE MATERIAL OF GERMAN LANGUAGE

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Abstract. *Today, due to the rapid development of medicine, the number of special medical terms is increasing significantly. The purpose of this article is to clarify the semantic features of medical terms on the example of the German language.*

Keywords: *asepsis, microscope, anamnesis, radiology, genetics, immunology, virology, nutrition, vitaminology.*

Introduction. In recent years, German studies have paid much attention to the description of the semantics of individual subsystems of the vocabulary of the language. These subsystems include special vocabulary.

Due to the intensive development of medical and biological knowledge, the number of special medical terms is increasing significantly. It should be noted that the strongest impetus for the formation of many terms is new discoveries. For example, many medical terms appeared in the language, especially since the eighteenth century, with the invention of microscope, the discovery of new microbiological dyes and the production of microscopic histological tools, the introduction anamnesis and asepsis etc. In addition, new branches of medicine are emerging, directly related to both medical science and branches of knowledge bordering on it. International cooperation between specialists from different countries is expanding, leading to the creation of an international medical lexical fund, consisting of specially selected and cultivated terms, term elements, nomenclature designations, abbreviations and symbols. In the twentieth century, specialties such as radiology, genetics, immunology, virology, nutrition, vitaminology and others. The creation of new medicines and drugs, the emergence of new medical equipment, the irreversible process of introduction into medicine laser technology and its computerization gives rise to the need to nominate special concepts and realities. Modern German medical terminology has reached As O. Jespersen points out, “any branch of science that does not stand still, but develops, must from time to time be of a new enormous size - 250,000 lexical units, and together with related disciplines - 500,000 (Wiese, 1984, S.15) * As a result of the information explosion - an unusually rapid growth in the flow of scientific and industrial information - a “terminological explosion” occurred - a sharp increase in the number of new terms.

Lack of attention to the spontaneous growth of medical terminology and the complication of the nature of terminological processes can lead to a “terminological flood” - a situation when the development of special vocabulary becomes uncontrollable. Therefore, the streamlining of medical vocabulary is of great importance for the mutual understanding of specialists (which is becoming increasingly difficult in connection with the specialization of sciences), the training of scientific personnel, the publication of scientific and reference literature, the development of international relations, the receipt and exchange of information, and the development of automated systems.

“Semantic features of medical terms”. Changes in the composition of synonymous and antonymic groups included in German medical terminology are associated with such tendencies

inherent in the language as tendencies towards differentiation, as well as towards the complication and enrichment of its structure.

Synonymous relations in medical terminology, unlike other terminology systems, are distinguished by their specificity due to the fact that the object of medicine (living matter) is only partially amenable to typification and unification, therefore synonymous terms make up a huge number. The degree of synonymy of terms varies. It is due to the differentiating function of synonymy. Along with the quality of different meanings, when determining the synonymy of terms, it is necessary to take into account the number of synonymous meanings. Synonymous lexemes, along with a certain semantic commonality, also have certain differences. The differentiating function manifests itself not only in relation to terms as a whole, but also in relation to their meanings. Moreover, these differences are not limited to whether synonymous relations concern basic or derived meanings. Sometimes lexemes enter into synonymous relationships only by derived meanings. In this case, certain differences in the degree of synonymy appear: it can be more or less or even minimal. In this regard, we can talk about relative synonymous connections between terms with the same meaning.

The sources of synonymy in the medical terminology of the German language are: the functioning of areal, dialect, word-formation synonyms, the presence of euphemism terms, professionalisms, obsolete, eponymous and borrowed terms.

Antonymy in German medical terminology is represented almost more widely than in the general literary language. This situation is explained by the fact that opposing concepts actually exist in science, and the opposition of concepts is an element of the scientific understanding of objects, an organizing principle. Antonymous as well as synonymous relations can be found in both single-valued and polysemous terms. In contrast to the antonymic connections of unambiguous terms, polysemantic lexical units can be characterized by various antonymic relations, for example, according to the main or derivative meaning, although unambiguous terms also act as antonyms for polysemantic lexemes, according to one or another meaning of the latter.

The terms of each individual terminology, including medical terminology, largely depend on the properties of OAS terminology, one of which is systematicity. Features of the development of terminology are determined, as it were, two-way - both by the properties of the terminology and the specificity of the terms.

The systematic nature of terminology is organically connected with its development. This unity ensures the identification of trends in the functioning of terminology: a tendency to intensify the process of borrowing, to the internationalization of vocabulary, its interaction with various lexical layers, to complicate the composition of terminology, a tendency towards nominalization, rationalization and saving of linguistic means, differentiation, integration, intellectualization and specialization.

These trends are manifested primarily in the quantitative development of terminology. The number of medical terms is increasing. The processes of borrowing and word formation play an important role here.

Foreign language vocabulary had a significant influence on the formation of German medical terminology in all periods of its existence. In the modern era of its development, tendencies towards the internationalization of languages and the intensification of borrowing processes appear especially clearly. Borrowings have different genetic origins, but the largest class

consists of terms that came from the English language, which is due to both extralinguistic reasons and the high prestige of the English language throughout the world.

The international nature of medical science predetermines the process of internationalization of borrowings, however, most internationalisms in German medical terminology were created on a Greco-Latin basis. Similar to native German medical terms, borrowed terms may exhibit semantic processes associated with changes in their scope of meaning.

Along with borrowing, word formation is a powerful source of development of German medical terminology. It is closely related to the tendency towards linguistic economy in signs conveying the content of an utterance, which is also inherent in the special vocabulary of the German language. This tendency is expressed in the widespread use of elliptical constructions and various kinds of abbreviations. Word formation is the most characteristic way of development of German medical terminology, which is explained by the peculiarities of the structure of the German language. Abbreviation has become one of the most productive means of forming new terms. However, the most productive means of forming terminology is compounding.

Trends towards the internationalization of vocabulary and the integration of languages explain the widespread use of cripple terms and eponym terms in German medical terminology. During their formation, the semantics (and structure) of the term are borrowed, although its material shell is built on the basis of the German language. Word-forming tracing papers filled German medical terminology at all stages of its development. This trend continues in our time. An equally important way of replenishing terminology with new terms is the formation of eponymous terms, which, despite intensive measures to eliminate them, continue to actively function.

Along with this, the terminology is replenished with words from commonly used vocabulary. Its replenishment with linguistic means of the national language occurs mainly through metaphorization and metonymization. These semantic processes contribute to the development of polysemy and homonymy.

Polysemy is a semantic relationship of internally related (motivated) meanings expressed by the forms of one word and creating a certain system. Systematicity is one of the most important features that distinguishes it from homonymy. The presence of polysemy in terminology suggests that the tendency towards unambiguity of lexical units is inferior to the tendency towards expanding the scope of their semantic content. The difference between polysemy and homonymy in medical terminology is established using the method of semantic analysis, as well as auxiliary criteria - grammatical and word-formation.

Despite the fact that lexicologists and terminologists-normalizers are constantly fighting against such phenomena as synonymy and polysemy, the latter inevitably accompanies term formation. These semantic phenomena can neither be ignored nor overcome, since it is impossible to separate the term from the real living linguistic matter. All semantic processes are subject to its linguistic laws, determined by the systematic nature of the lexical level of language. Systematicity, in particular, manifests itself in the relationships between the meanings of terms, which change with the development of terminology.

No matter how different the meanings of a particular medical term may be, there is something in common that maintains their unity within the system. It lies in a certain connection of values with each other. When identifying these connections, it is necessary to rely on the underlying meaning. It may coincide with the etymological one. However, there are cases when the etymological meaning is absent in the structure of the term or becomes secondary, since during

the terminology of commonly used words, a decrease or expansion occurs, as well as the disappearance or alternation of their basic and derivative meanings. The semantic structure of different terms develops differently.

Being an element of terminology, the term enters into various linguistic relationships with other lexical units, without losing, however, its inherent originality and system of meanings, since the term represents the unity of the general and the separate. It is differentiated in semantic relations, in particular, in synonymous ones. It should be noted that unambiguous medical terms are also not without linguistic connections. In terms of synonymy, they interact not only with each other, but also with polysemantic terms, both in the main and in the derived meanings of the latter.

Synonymous lexemes, along with a certain semantic commonality, also have certain differences. The differentiating function manifests itself not only in relation to terms as a whole, but also in relation to their meanings. Moreover, these differences are not limited to whether synonymous relations concern basic or derived meanings. Sometimes lexemes enter into synonymous relationships only by derived meanings, and in this case certain differences in the degree of synonymy appear: it can be more or less, or even minimal. In this regard, we can talk about relative synonymous connections of lexical units of German medical terminology according to the same meaning.

Synonymy reflects a conscious search and translation of linguistic means for a more precise designation where the primary nomination has already been made. At the same time, one can notice some arbitrariness in the choice of borrowings and words of the general literary German language when nominating scientific objects. To a large extent, this is facilitated by the associations evoked by objects. As a result, one object receives not one, but several names, which contributes to the emergence of a large number of synonyms registered in modern German medical dictionaries.

Medical terms enter into antonymic relationships, which denote opposing concepts related by contrast. In contrast to the antonymic connections of unambiguous terms, polysemantic lexical units can be characterized by various antonymic relations (for example, according to the main or derivative meaning), although unambiguous terms also act as antonyms for polysemantic lexemes, according to one or another meaning of the latter.

Conclusion. The main role in terminology is played by the processes of integration, the complication of the structure of terms and terminology in general, with a dialectical connection between stability and dynamics. The openness of terminology is based on the assimilation, preservation, archaization and development of terms that contribute to its renewal, improvement, and adaptation to new functioning needs.

Thus, the evolution of terms and their relationships does not imply a simple change in the state of German medical terminology, but functional changes that provide variability with stable trends, which are characterized by a complex set of various processes and interactions that accompany it.

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